

Electrochemical Synthesis of Benzylacetamide by Oxidation of Phenylacetic Acid

P. N. GUPTA* and ANJU RAINA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kashmir, Srinagar 190 006

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Electrochemical oxidation of phenylacetic acid to benzylacetamide on carbon anode in nominally wet acetonitrile has been found to give 68% yield. The effect of potential, pH and temperature on the reaction revealed interesting features which throw light on the proposed mechanism.

A low yield (7.2%) of benzylacetamide via acylation of amines with amides or esters in a two-step conventional procedure has been reported¹ despite rigorous conditions of temperature, pressure and time. Electrochemical oxidation of phenylacetic acid in nominally wet acetonitrile containing 0.5% H₂O on carbon anode and copper cathode employing a low constant potential maintained potentiostatically has been worked out to give a substantially high yield (68%) in a reasonable span of time. The reaction mechanism was adequately studied by determining activation energy of the reaction from the dependence of current density on temperature, pH and by varying the potential of the working electrode.

Experimental

Acetonitrile (Merck) was purified by standard method². Tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP) was recrystallised twice from water and dried in an oven (110°) and kept in desiccator. Phenylacetic acid (Merck) was further recrystallised from 50% alcohol.

Procedure: Laboratory scale electrolysis was carried out in a divided glass cell at controlled potential using a Wenking LB 81M potentiostat. Interference of electromagnetic radiations was minimised by covering the instrument with perspex sheet, connecting wires with Al-foils and conducting the experiment as far away as possible from electrical installations so as to record genuine potentiostatic readings.

Carbon anode (1.3 cm dia × 1 cm; surface area 4.1 cm²) and Cu plate (2 × 2 cm) as cathode were used. The reference electrode Ag/Ag⁺ (0.1 M) was connected to the anode compartment with a Luggin capillary. Agitation of the electrolytic mixture was performed by magnetic stirrer at 1000 rpm. pH of the solution was adjusted to 7.2 (unless specified otherwise) by adding HClO₄ or NaOH solution. Temperature of the cell (25 ± 0.5° unless specified otherwise) was controlled by a Ultrathermostat

(NBE) GDR. TEAP (0.3 M) solution in acetonitrile was placed in the ratio of 4 : 1 in anode and cathode compartments, respectively. Phenylacetic acid (0.1 M) was added to the anode compartment. The potential was maintained at +1.70–1.75 V, with initial current generally 200–190 mA. The background in these was less than 1 mA. Electrolysis was usually discontinued when the current dropped to 4–20 mA (depending on pH) which generally took on an average 30 h.

Cyclic voltammograms were recorded with a multipurpose electrochemical module (CSIO, India) coupled with omnigraphic 2000 x-y/t recorder using 0.4 cm² carbon as working electrode.

Work up :

The crude electrolysed mixture was extracted with ether (4 × 50 ml). The combined ether extracts were extracted with 20% NaOH to weakly alkaline reaction and allowed to stand for 5–6 h, then extracted in three portions of 1N HCl. The precipitate of phenylacetic acid was removed and the extract evaporated to dryness. Residual mixture of benzylacetamide and NaCl extracted with ten times its volume of 67% methanol + 33% CHCl₃, salted out NaCl while benzylacetamide dissolved. Removal of the solvent by distillation using water-pump with heat supplied by a bath at 80°, revealed crystals of benzylacetamide. The yield was 10.1 g (m.p. 58–9°) after recrystallisation from ether. Analysis by vpc of ether solution indicated the presence of 10.11 g of benzylacetamide.

Chemical yield (calculated at pH 7.2) :

$$\% \text{ Yield} = (\text{actual yield/theoretical yield}) \times 100 \\ = (10.1/14.9) \times 100 = 67.78\%$$

Current yield (calculated at pH 7.2) :

$$\text{Amount of electricity spent} = 6 \text{ Ah}/26.8 \times 2 \text{ Ah} \\ = 0.1119 \text{ F}$$

$$\text{Theoretical yield by Faraday's law} \\ = 149 \times 0.1119 = 16.67$$

$$\% \text{ Current yield} = (10.1/16.67) \times 100 = 60.55\%$$

Results and Discussion

The sample recrystallised from 50% alcohol was subjected to elemental analysis and purity test⁸. It compares well within 1–2% of the observed and reported values⁴: λ_{max} 258 nm; pK_a , 4.3 (H_2O); m.p. 59°; N, 9.41%.

The number of electrons consumed in acetonitrile, 0.3 M TEAP at pH 7.2 containing 1×10^{-4} – 1×10^{-3} M phenylacetic acid was determined coulometrically. Measurement of the decrease in concentration of electrolysed compound with time and the integration of the current consumed in electrolysis made it possible to calculate the involvement of number of electrons $n=2$.

Temperature dependence and activation energy of process: It is noticed from the polarisation curves, $\log i$ vs E , (Fig. 1) that temperature increases hardly affects oxidation pattern of phenylacetic acid; a regular and parallel shift observed as temperature is enhanced from 10 to 35°. Attempts to predict

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on $\log i$ vs E curves of (0.1 M) phenylacetic acid: (1) 10°, (2) 15°, (3) 20°, (4) 25°, (5) 30° and (6) 35°; solvent CH_3CN , pH 7.2.

quantitative variation in standard free energy of activation⁹ calculated from the relation $\log i$ vs $1/T$ in a potential range of 1.40–1.70 V (which comprises 90% of the wave) revealed a value of 52.8 ± 10 kJ mol⁻¹. Therefore, the dependence of the reaction on voltage applied is substantially high which is contrary to expectation reported by Johnson *et al.*⁸ and this may be explained by the fact that polarisation curves are shifted with increasing temperature towards lower anodic potential.

Effect of pH on current yield: Experiments were run in which pH has been changed (from 4.8 to 7.2 and also 9.2) in an unbuffered solution at identical potentiostatic conditions, concentration and temperature. Current yield (Y) results were perturbed, e.g., at pH 4.8, Y is 58% at pH 7.2, Y 61%, and at pH 9.2, Y 45%, the chemical yields were higher by a margin of 8–10% compared to the former. The interpretation of data does not

seem to be quite straight forward in that all of H^+ alone does not suffice possible reasons for anomalous behaviour of current yield. Side reactions (both by H and OH) might be responsible for build-up of benzylacetamide from reaction process causing pronounced scavenging of H^+ in secondary reactions which subsequently lead to resultant observed reduction in yield particularly at pH 9.2. Obviously the selection of pH 7.2 is better, although the choice was arbitrary.

Effect of solvent: Solvents play a peculiar and decisive role in the product formation vis-a-vis yield⁷, e.g. in MeOH bibenzyl, in 67% MeOH+33% pyridine benzylmethyl ether and methylphenylacetate, and in 67% H_2O +33% pyridine benzylalcohol and benzaldehyde are the major products reported. Evidence in support of this observation⁸ seems to have been sought with variation in either supporting electrolyte or the water concentration in acetonitrile to produce bibenzyl, benzylacetamide and benzyl alcohol. Under the optimum conditions the major product is benzylacetamide with no evidence of bibenzyl in particular.

Cyclic voltammetry: Cyclic voltammogram of phenylacetic acid at carbon electrode in acetonitrile and 0.3 M TEAP revealed single two-electron anodic wave having peak potential E_p , +1.65 V at $0.5 V s^{-1}$, with no complementary cathodic wave on reverse scan. The study of effect of enhanced sweep rate from 0.025 to $1.5 V s^{-1}$ on the peak potential and peak current showed a shift in E_p towards more anodic potential while cathodic peak remained absent invariably; similarly, the peak current i_p was increased. Further, i_p showed an increase with increase in concentration of the reactant and current function ($i_p/\nu^{1/2} C$) remained constant suggesting the process to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. Similar behaviour was noticed earlier by the authors⁹ in case of electrochemical studies on diazaphenanthrene.

Appearance of another small anodic peak at a sweep rate $\nu \geq 2.0 V s^{-1}$ could be attributed to the short-lived¹⁰ product forming intermediate presumably benzyl radical.

Electrode mechanism: The following scheme may be proposed for oxidation reaction (pH 7.2),

Generally electron transfer occurs in single steps but the absence of dimer, bibenzyl in solution strongly favours a single $2e$ decarboxylation step as the initial stage of reaction. Further, benzyl radical generated, if any, by a process of single-electron transfer possess a relatively low ionisation potential¹¹, consequently gets converted into benzyl cation due to the imposed oxidation potential. The cation formation is virtually favoured on carbon electrode surface due to presence of additional binding forces (paramagnetic centres residing on the electrode) which bind the benzyl radicals to undergo further electron transfer. Nucleophilic acetonitrile attacks benzyl cation to give nitrilium salts (supported by the work of Ebersson and Nyberg¹²) which hydrolyses to benzylacetamide.

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References

1. S. MINORU, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1950, **70**, 553.
2. D. OLARK, F. FLEISCHMANN and D. PLATCHEK, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1972, **36**, 137.
3. P. N. GUPTA and A. RAINA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 495; *Bull. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1988, **4**, 989.
4. "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", ed. R. C. WEAST, 60th. ed., CRC Press, Florida, 1979.
5. J. O'M. BOCKRIS and A. K. N. REDDY, "Modern Electrochemistry", Plenum, New York, 1970, Vol. 2, p. 872.
6. J. W. JOHNSON, H. WROBLOVA and J. O'M. BOCKRIS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1964, **9**, 639.
7. S. D. ROSS and M. FINKELSTEIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1969, **34**, 2923, and references therein.
8. V. D. PARKER and B. E. BURGERT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, 2411.
9. P. N. GUPTA and A. RAINA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1988, **78**, 317.
10. D. D. MACDONALD, "Transient Techniques in Electrochemistry", Plenum, New York, 1977, p. 186.
11. A. G. HARRISON, P. KEBARLE and F. P. LOSSING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 777.
12. L. EBERSON and K. NYBERG, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1964, **18**, 1567.